

- 1- https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdyZJRYB1_bjfiu_0mJNHUzhPo27sh74x2pX5I34cjXU0R3Q/viewform
- 2- https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdc_PckWlOoH46Kn3ClkrOjo4oMyQ-d_eZUMQ8-OSXccQLJUQ/viewform
- 3- <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdE46nMBxAMqRxOH3I57MYGetv0WM-WbRmuTCndjIazdotOWQ/viewform>
- 4- https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeqBShqBm8zaARzOI8plumj1krmHONjq_bbHPCnRmAMrsrRqQ/viewform

These questionnaires were distributed as part of the project "Multi-perspective approach to the phenomenon of migration in Albania. This project was implemented in the period 2024-2026. During the project, a specific questionnaire was designed and implemented, as well as a "Didactic Guide for students returning from emigration, for the pre-university education system."

Such works have not been carried out to date in our institution (UNIEL) regarding this phenomenon. This has made such a study particularly necessary, especially in anticipation of the need to review study programmes in pre-university education and, more specifically, in teacher education programmes at our university. The primary aim of this project is to construct a comprehensive historical, educational, socio-cultural, and media framework to support the integration of children returning from emigration into Albanian society. This objective is pursued through the development of supplementary materials for the Albanian pre-university education system. Within this context, the preparation of a didactic guide for pre-university teachers was considered essential, in response to an identified gap in the education system regarding the development of key competencies necessary for individual formation and active participation in society. This study also introduces innovation in line with the policies and recommendations of the Council of Europe, particularly those promoting a multi-perspective approach in schools for the development of essential life competencies. This guide addresses the needs of teachers, pedagogues, and policymakers by offering practical tools and strategic guidance aimed at fostering sustainable educational development.

This questionnaire was distributed in the period December 2024 - February 2025 in several municipalities of Albania, and a total of 1030 participants participated, of whom 725 teachers, 158 students, 107 parents and 40 university students.